

Fatigue Crack Propagation Behavior and Mechanism of Al/Al₂O₃/SiC Hybrid Metal Matrix Composites

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ABSTRACT

The fatigue crack propagation behavior and fatigue mechanism of a squeeze-cast Al-1Mg-0.6Si reinforced with alumina short fiber and SiC whisker has been investigated. For the fabrication of Al/Al₂O₃ and Al/Al₂O₃/SiC hybrid composites, Al 6061 aluminum alloy was used as a matrix. Al/Al₂O₃ and Al/Al₂O₃/SiC composites with 15% volume fractions were fabricated by the squeeze infiltration method. Tensile and fatigue crack growth (FCG) rate tests at room temperature were performed. FCG rate behaviors were represented by following relationships ; 1) $da/dN - \Delta K$, 2) $K_{ci}/K_{max} - \Delta K$. Furthermore, fatigue mechanism studied by fractography study was also discussed in comparison with the unreinforced alloy and metal matrix composites.

Key words : hybrid metal matrix composite, squeeze infiltration method, fatigue crack propagation, fatigue mechanism, fractography

INTRODUCTION

Recently, a great deal of interest has been shown in the use of discontinuously reinforced metal matrix composites(MMCs) for primary structural applications. Composites can offer distinct technological advantages over continuously reinforced MMCs, as well as cost advantages due to lower fiber costs and fabrication methodology using the squeeze infiltration method[1-4]. The failure of a material originates from cracks initiated by the flaws and notches. Cracks propagate according to complex crack propagation mechanisms. It is important to confirm the mechanism of fracture to improve the material characteristics.

A lot of studies have recently been undertaken concerning the fatigue crack growth properties of aluminum alloys with either SiC particulate or whisker reinforcement. In most cases, the incorporation of ceramic reinforcement has resulted in higher values of the threshold stress intensity range ΔK_{th} , below which fatigue cracks are non-propagating. Some results, however, suggest a decreased resistance to fatigue crack growth in the composites compared with the unreinforced matrix. In one study the composites investigated were found to exhibit faster crack growth rates in the paris region than the unreinforced matrix alloy[5, 6]. In other words, comparisons between different composites and aluminum alloys are difficult to make since only a few published reports include detailed microstructural characterization of the material[7]. The various manufacturing methods of composites currently in use dictate that large microstructural

variations between different materials are to be expected. Up to now, extensive research has been done on the fatigue crack propagation of discontinuous MMCs reinforced by the addition of one kind reinforcement, such as Al_2O_3 , SiC, and C, etc.[8 - 12]. However, little attention was paid to the effect of hybrid metal matrix composites on fatigue crack propagation behavior.

Therefore, the authors conducted the experimental study to investigate the fatigue crack propagation behavior for the MMCs manufactured by the squeeze infiltration method, and also to compare these behaviors of hybrid composites to unreinforced alloy and Al/ Al_2O_3 composite. The objectives of this study are to examine the mechanism of fatigue crack initiation and crack growth rate in hybrid composites, in terms of crack closure rate, K_{cl}/K_{max} , as well as through fractographic studies of the fracture surface. Another important goal of this study is to provide the fatigue mechanism of crack initiation and propagation mechanisms in hybrid composites using an optical microscope.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

MATERIALS AND FABRICATION

For the fabrication of Al/ Al_2O_3 and Al/ Al_2O_3 /SiC composites, a 6061 aluminum alloy was used as a matrix. Alumina fibers, " Saffil " RF Grade, from ICI Co. and SiC whiskers, Tokaiwhisker from TEXTRON Specialty Materials Co., were obtained. Their specifications are listed in Table 1. Al/ Al_2O_3 and Al/ Al_2O_3 /SiC composites were fabricated by squeeze infiltration method. The 50-ton hydraulic press and the cylindrical mold were used. Aluminum melts and the preform were overheated to 800 °C and 500 °C, respectively. Applied pressure was 25 MPa and the ram speed was 2.0 m/s. During solidification, the pressure was maintained for 1 minute.

Table. 1 Specifications of alumina short fiber and SiC whisker

Material	Density (g/cm ³)	Diameter (μ m)	Length (μ m)	Aspect ratio(l/d)	Tensile strength(GPa)	Young's modulus (GPa)
Al_2O_3	3.3	6.6	200	25	2	310
SiC _w	3.2	0.6	15	25	3 - 14	400 - 700

TENSILE AND FATIGUE CRACK PROPAGATION TESTS

Room temperature tensile tests were performed with UTM system (SHIMADZU, 5 ton, Japan). To measure strains, extensometer was attached in the center of the gage length section. They were displacement controlled and the displacement rate was 0.5 mm / min. Specimens were machined perpendicular to the direction of the applied pressure. Round specimens of 12 mm diameter and 25 mm gage length were used.

The fatigue crack propagation tests were conducted with an R value of 0.1 using a sinusoidal wave form at a frequency of 10 Hz at room temperature. Crack length measurements were performed using a travelling light microscope (with resolution of 1 μ m or resolution < 5 μ m) on

the surface of the specimens. A load - shedding procedure was used for the determination of ΔK_{th} . The stress intensity range that gave a growth rate $da/dN < 10^{-9}$ m/cycle was taken as the threshold level. A clip gauge mounted at the crack mouth was used for the closure measurements. The closure load P_{cl} was defined as the point of intersection between the two straight branches of the compliance curve of the sample. The fatigue crack growth experiments were performed on compact tension (CT) type specimens of 48 mm width and 7 mm thickness for the cast ingot.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

FABRICATION BY SQUEEZE CASTING ROUTE

Al/Al₂O₃-vol.15% and Al/Al/Al₂O₃-vol.10%/SiC-vol.5% hybrid composites were successfully fabricated by the squeeze casting method. The optimum temperature was obtained as follows. The actual preheating temperature of the mold and preform was 500 °C and that of the lower cap was 500 °C because the mold is assembled in air before setting the preform into the mold. For minimum fiber damages, the applied pressure has to be as low as possible. 25 MPa for Al/Al/Al₂O₃ composites and Al/Al/Al₂O₃/SiC composites is the minimum for perfect infiltration up to 15% volume fraction of discontinuous MMCs. The proper design helps to apply the pressure uniformly and to obtain casts with the perfect infiltration and less pores. In this study, many tapered holes with 2mm diameter were drilled at the bottom of the low cap.

Typical microstructures of Al/Al₂O₃ and Al/Al/Al₂O₃/SiC composites are represented in Fig. 1. To verify the distribution of reinforcements, microstructures of Al/Al/Al₂O₃ and Al/Al/Al₂O₃/SiC composites were observed through the optical microscope. As shown in figure, surfaces normal to, and parallel to the pressure direction, were examined to identify the effects of applied pressure on the orientation of reinforcements. It is shown that uniform distributions of reinforcements and good bondings between reinforcements and the matrix alloy are achieved. And specially, alumina short fibers and SiC whiskers are uniformly distributed along the height of the cast, i.e., negligible variations of local volume fractions. Insignificant variations of local volume fractions are due to the homogeneity of the preform which can be obtained by the adequate pressure and the sufficient mixing of reinforcements.

Fig. 1 Microstructures a) Al/Al₂O₃ and b) Al/Al/Al₂O₃/SiC hybrid composite fabricated by squeeze infiltration method

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

Many reports on the characterization of mechanical properties of discontinuous MMCs have been available. According to this work, mechanical properties, such as Young's modulus and strength, have been improved about 10 - 80% by incorporation of reinforcements[13-15]. However, ductility has deteriorated remarkably along with increasing the content of reinforcements.

In this study, these results of the tensile properties of the materials used are given in Table 2. On the whole, it was found that mechanical properties, such as tensile and 0.2% yield strength, Young's modulus, of Al/Al₂O₃/SiC hybrid composite, were improved considerably compared with those of unreinforced matrix alloy. The elastic modulus of Al/Al₂O₃/SiC hybrid composite was improved about 13 % by the addition of SiC whisker reinforcement, compared with that of the Al/Al₂O₃ composite. Ultimate tensile strength of Al/Al₂O₃/SiC hybrid composite was also slightly improved as SiC whiskers were incorporated. On the contrary, 0.2% yield strength of Al/Al₂O₃/SiC_w hybrid composite showed less than that of Al/Al₂O₃ composite. Ductility deteriorated remarkably by addition of hybrid reinforcements, but somewhat improved in the Al/Al₂O₃ composite. From these results, it is found that the addition of SiC whisker to Al/Al₂O₃ composite gives rise to improvement of the mechanical properties. The SiC whisker additions were seen to be more effective in strengthening than adding a single species of Al₂O₃ fibers.

Table. 2 Tensile properties of squeeze cast materials investigated

Material	Young' s modulus (GPa)	0.2% Yield Strength (MPa)	Tensile strength(MPa)	Elongation (%)
Al6061	62.0	188	277	7.6
Al/Al ₂ O ₃	70.1	310	385	2.1
Al/Al ₂ O ₃ /SiC	76.7	285	399	4.4

FATIGUE CRACK PROPAGATION BEHAVIORS

In many works MMCs were found to have superior fatigue crack growth properties to those of the corresponding matrix alloys in the near threshold region. It is reported that this advantage generally diminishes when higher crack growth rate is considered. The fatigue threshold levels of composites are higher than those of the corresponding matrices[5,6,9]. However, comparisons between different composites and aluminum alloys are difficult to make since only a few published papers include detailed microstructural characterization of the material. The various manufacturing methods of composites currently in use dictate that large microstructural variations between different materials are to be expected. This means that fatigue crack growth behavior of MMCs might be sensitive to actual manufacturing methods, such as the squeeze casting and powder metallurgy route.

Fig. 2 illustrates the relationships between fatigue crack growth rate, da/dN and stress intensity factor range, ΔK compared with the unreinforced matrix alloy and metal matrix composites. As shown in this figure, the fatigue crack growth rates of Al/Al₂O₃ and Al/Al₂O₃/SiC_w composites are seen to be almost the same. However, in the present study, metal matrix composites exhibit inferior fatigue crack resistance to the unreinforced alloy. That is, the effect of the SiC whisker on the fatigue crack propagation characteristics in the Al/Al₂O₃/SiC_w composites appears deteriorated here for all stress intensity factor ranges compared with characteristics of the

unreinforced matrix alloy. Similar results were obtained by Logsdon and Liaw. They found that metal matrix composites had similar threshold stress intensity values but a lower resistance to crack propagation compared to wrought aluminum alloy. And when ΔK becomes higher, the fatigue crack growth rate of metal matrix composites increases rapidly and exceeds that of the unreinforced alloy. Meanwhile, above 10^{-7} m/cycles the fatigue crack growth of the metal matrix composites is slightly accelerated compared with that of the unreinforced matrix alloy.

Fig. 2 Relationship between fatigue crack growth rate and stress intensity factor range

Fig. 3 shows the relationship between crack closure rate (K_{cl}/K_{max}) and ΔK , where K_{max} is the maximum stress intensity factor and K_{cl} is the value at which crack tip just appears to close. Distinct ranges of fatigue crack closure which depend predominantly upon the value K_{max} with variation of ΔK . Here, crack closure K_{cl} is subtracted from nominal values of ΔK and da/dN is plotted as a function of effective stress intensity range ΔK_{ef} ($K_{max} - K_{cl}$). As shown in this figure, K_{cl}/K_{max} of the unreinforced alloy decreases linearly with increasing ΔK , but different behavior appears in metal matrix composites. That is, K_{cl}/K_{max} of the Al/Al₂O₃ and the Al/Al₂O₃/SiC composites decreases rapidly with increasing ΔK compared with that of the unreinforced matrix alloy. K_{cl}/K_{max} of the Al/Al₂O₃/SiC composite shows a nearly constant K_{cl}/K_{max} level above ΔK value of 7.84 MPa \sqrt{m} . And then K_{cl}/K_{max} drastically decrease with decreasing ΔK below ΔK value of 9.46 MPa \sqrt{m} . This is due to crack closure induced by either fracture surface roughness or oxide. These tendencies of crack closure become more severe with the addition of SiC whisker. In case of Al/Al₂O₃ composite, K_{cl}/K_{max} shows a rapid decrease until above ΔK value of 8 MPa \sqrt{m} and then indicates a slow decrease, compared with the crack closure rate of the Al 6061 alloy.

In the present study, the threshold levels of materials used for investigation as follows : Al 6061 ; 8.33 MPa \sqrt{m} , Al/Al₂O₃ composite ; 7.01 MPa \sqrt{m} , Al/Al₂O₃/SiC composite; 6.22 MPa \sqrt{m} . The effect of reinforcements on crack propagate resistance as shown by micrographic analysis has been discussed in detail later on.

Fig. 3 Relationship between crack closure rate and stress intensity factor range

FATIGUE MECHANISM

Fig. 4 shows the crack pass morphology of unreinforced matrix alloy observed through the optical microscope. This figure illustrates the typical fatigue crack profiles observed during long crack growth. The crack profiles of the unreinforced matrix alloy display fatigue crack propagation behavior linearly and smoothly. The shape of fatigue crack growth of matrix alloy shows intergranular microvoid coalescence passing through the grain boundary of matrix alloy.

Fig. 4 Optical microscope profile of crack path in unreinforced matrix alloy

Fig. 5 illustrates the crack pass profile of Al/Al₂O₃/SiC hybrid composite observed through the optical microscope. On the whole, in the Al/Al₂O₃/SiC composite the crack tends to avoid the SiC whiskers thereby promoting crack deflection. It is expected that crack deflection enhances

crack closure due to the wedging phenomenon, or so called roughness induced crack closure. The fatigue crack growth tends to bypass SiC whiskers microscopically and propagate around the whisker rich region, so that the fracture surfaces have very rough features showing under high magnification. Thus Al/Al₂O₃/SiC hybrid composite demonstrates that the more severe crack closure occurs as shown in this figure. At near threshold levels, the crack follows a path that tends to pass the reinforcements. This can produce a inferior crack growth resistance due to the increase of the presence of debris by the roughness induced closure and the crack deflection. Being unexpected, these are reasons that the fatigue crack growth rate of the metal matrix composites is accelerated compared with that of the unreinforced alloy. On the other hand, many fractured SiC whisker or alumina short fibers covered with the matrix alloy were observed on the fracture surface in Al/Al₂O₃/SiC composites showing roughness. This indicates that a fatigue crack propagates unstably along the whisker matrix interface or through the fractured whisker because of rich SiC whiskers ahead of the crack tip.

Fig. 5 Optical microscope profile of crack path in Al/Al₂O₃/SiC composite

CONCLUSIONS

- 1) Metal matrix composites was successfully fabricated by squeeze casting method. Optimum processing conditions for squeeze casting were obtained. From their microstructures, it was found that uniform distribution of reinforcements and good bonding were achieved.
- 2) Mechanical properties, such as tensile and 0.2% yield strength, Young's modulus, of Al/Al₂O₃/SiC hybrid composite, were improved considerably compared with those of Al/Al₂O₃ composite and unreinforced matrix alloy. The addition of SiC whisker to Al/Al₂O₃ composite gave rise to improvement of the mechanical properties.
- 3) The fatigue crack growth rates of Al/Al₂O₃ and Al/Al₂O₃/SiC_w composites obtained almost the same results. Metal matrix composites exhibited inferior fatigue crack resistance compared to the unreinforced alloy. This resulted in inferior crack growth resistance due to the increase of the presence of debris. The effect of the SiC whisker on the fatigue crack propagation characteristics in the Al/Al₂O₃/SiC_w composites were not improved here compared with that in Al/Al₂O₃ composite.

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